

R colors

1	white	#FFFFFF	255	255	255
2	aliceblue	#F0F8FF	240	248	255
3	antiquewhite	#FAEBD7	250	235	215
4	antiquewhite1	#FFEFDB	255	239	219
5	antiquewhite2	#EEDFCC	238	223	204
6	antiquewhite3	#CDC0B0	205	192	176
7	antiquewhite4	#8B8378	139	131	120
8	aquamarine	#7FFFD4	127	255	212
9	aquamarine1	#7FFFD4	127	255	212
10	aquamarine2	#76EEC6	118	238	198
11	aquamarine3	#66CDAA	102	205	170
12	aquamarine4	#458B74	69	139	116
13	azure	#F0FFFF	240	255	255
14	azure1	#F0FFFF	240	255	255
15	azure2	#E0EEEE	224	238	238
16	azure3	#C1CDCD	193	205	205
17	azure4	#838B8B	131	139	139
18	beige	#F5F5DC	245	245	220
19	bisque	#FFE4C4	255	228	196
20	bisque1	#FFE4C4	255	228	196
21	bisque2	#EED5B7	238	213	183
22	bisque3	#CDB79E	205	183	158
23	bisque4	#8B7D6B	139	125	107
24	black	#000000	0	0	0
25	blanchedalmond	#FFEBCD	255	235	205
26	blue	#0000FF	0	0	255
27	blue1	#0000FF	0	0	255
28	blue2	#0000EE	0	0	238
29	blue3	#0000CD	0	0	205
30	blue4	#00008B	0	0	139
31	blueviolet	#8A2BE2	138	43	226
32	brown	#A52A2A	165	42	42
33	brown1	#FF4040	255	64	64
34	brown2	#EE3B3B	238	59	59
35	brown3	#CD3333	205	51	51
36	brown4	#8B2323	139	35	35
37	burlywood	#DEB887	222	184	135
38	burlywood1	#FFD39B	255	211	155
39	burlywood2	#EEC591	238	197	145
40	burlywood3	#CDA77D	205	170	125
41	burlywood4	#8B7355	139	115	85
42	cadetblue	#5F9EA0	95	158	160
43	cadetblue1	#98F5FF	152	245	255
44	cadetblue2	#8EE5EE	142	229	238
45	cadetblue3	#7AC5CD	122	197	205
46	cadetblue4	#53868B	83	134	139
47	chartreuse	#7FFF00	127	255	0
48	chartreuse1	#7FFF00	127	255	0
49	chartreuse2	#76EE00	118	238	0
50	chartreuse3	#66CD00	102	205	0
51	chartreuse4	#458B00	69	139	0
52	chocolate	#D2691E	210	105	30
53	chocolate1	#FF7F24	255	127	36
54	chocolate2	#EE7621	238	118	33
55	chocolate3	#CD661D	205	102	29
56	chocolate4	#8B4513	139	69	19
57	coral	#FF7F50	255	127	80
58	coral1	#FF7256	255	114	86
59	coral2	#EE6A50	238	106	80
60	coral3	#CD5B45	205	91	69
61	coral4	#8B3E2F	139	62	47
62	cornflowerblue	#6495ED	100	149	237
63	cornsilk	#FFF8DC	255	248	220
64	cornsilk1	#FFF8DC	255	248	220
65	cornsilk2	#EEE8CD	238	232	205
66	cornsilk3	#CDC8B1	205	200	177
67	cornsilk4	#8B8878	139	136	120
68	cyan	#00FFFF	0	255	255
69	cyan1	#00FFFF	0	255	255
70	cyan2	#00EEEE	0	238	238
71	cyan3	#00CDCD	0	205	205
72	cyan4	#008B8B	0	139	139
73	darkblue	#00008B	0	0	139
74	darkcyan	#008B8B	0	139	139
75	darkgoldenrod	#8B6914	184	134	11
76	darkgoldenrod1	#FF8C00	255	185	15
77	darkgoldenrod2	#EAD0E0	238	173	14
78	darkgoldenrod3	#CD950C	205	149	12
79	darkgoldenrod4	#8B6508	139	101	8
80	darkgray	#A9A9A9	169	169	169
81	darkgreen	#006400	0	100	0
82	darkgrey	#A9A9A9	169	169	169
83	darkkhaki	#BDB76B	189	183	107
84	darkmagenta	#8B008B	139	0	139
85	darkolivegreen	#556B2F	85	107	47
86	darkolivegreen1	#CAFF70	202	255	112
87	darkolivegreen2	#BCEE68	188	238	104
88	darkolivegreen3	#A2CD5A	162	205	90
89	darkolivegreen4	#6E8B3D	110	139	61
90	darkorange	#FF8C00	255	140	0
91	darkorange1	#FF7F00	255	127	0
92	darkorange2	#EE7600	238	118	0
93	darkorange3	#CD6600	205	102	0
94	darkorange4	#8B4500	139	69	0
95	darkorchid	#9932CC	153	50	204
96	darkorchid1	#BF3EFF	191	62	255
97	darkorchid2	#B23AEE	178	58	238
98	darkorchid3	#9A32CD	154	50	205
99	darkorchid4	#68228B	104	34	139
100	darkred	#8B0000	139	0	0

R colors

101	darksalmon	#E9967A	233	150	122
102	darkseagreen	#8FBC8F	143	188	143
103	darkseagreen1	#C1FFC1	193	255	193
104	darkseagreen2	#B4EEB4	180	238	180
105	darkseagreen3	#9BCD9B	155	205	155
106	darkseagreen4	#698B69	105	139	105
107	darkslateblue	#483D8B	72	61	139
108	darkslategray	#2F4F4F	47	79	79
109	darkslategray1	#97FFFF	151	255	255
110	darkslategray2	#8DEEEE	141	238	238
111	darkslategray3	#79CDCD	121	205	205
112	darkslategray4	#528B8B	82	139	139
113	darkslategrey	#2F4F4F	47	79	79
114	darkturquoise	#00CED1	0	206	209
115	darkviolet	#9400D3	148	0	211
116	deeppink	#FF1493	255	20	147
117	deeppink1	#FF1493	255	20	147
118	deeppink2	#EE1289	238	18	137
119	deeppink3	#CD1076	205	16	118
120	deeppink4	#8B0A50	139	10	80
121	deepskyblue	#00BFFF	0	191	255
122	deepskyblue1	#00BFFF	0	191	255
123	deepskyblue2	#00B2EE	0	178	238
124	deepskyblue3	#009ACD	0	154	205
125	deepskyblue4	#00688B	0	104	139
126	dimgray	#696969	105	105	105
127	dimgrey	#696969	105	105	105
128	dodgerblue	#1E90FF	30	144	255
129	dodgerblue1	#1E90FF	30	144	255
130	dodgerblue2	#1C86EE	28	134	238
131	dodgerblue3	#1874CD	24	116	205
132	dodgerblue4	#104E8B	16	78	139
133	firebrick	#B22222	178	34	34
134	firebrick1	#FF3030	255	48	48
135	firebrick2	#EE2C2C	238	44	44
136	firebrick3	#CD2626	205	38	38
137	firebrick4	#8B1A1A	139	26	26
138	floralwhite	#FFFAF0	255	250	240
139	forestgreen	#228B22	34	139	34
140	gainsboro	#DCDCDC	220	220	220
141	ghostwhite	#F8F8FF	248	248	255
142	gold	#FFD700	255	215	0
143	gold1	#FFD700	255	215	0
144	gold2	#EEC900	238	201	0
145	gold3	#CDAD00	205	173	0
146	gold4	#8B7500	139	117	0
147	goldenrod	#DAA520	218	165	32
148	goldenrod1	#FFC125	255	193	37
149	goldenrod2	#EEB422	238	180	34
150	goldenrod3	#CD9B1D	205	155	29

151	goldenrod4	#8B6914	139	105	20
152	gray	#BEBEBE	190	190	190
153	gray0	#000000	0	0	0
154	gray1	#030303	3	3	3
155	gray2	#050505	5	5	5
156	gray3	#080808	8	8	8
157	gray4	#0A0A0A	10	10	10
158	gray5	#0D0D0D	13	13	13
159	gray6	#0F0F0F	15	15	15
160	gray7	#121212	18	18	18
161	gray8	#141414	20	20	20
162	gray9	#171717	23	23	23
163	gray10	#1A1A1A	26	26	26
164	gray11	#1C1C1C	28	28	28
165	gray12	#1F1F1F	31	31	31
166	gray13	#212121	33	33	33
167	gray14	#242424	36	36	36
168	gray15	#262626	38	38	38
169	gray16	#292929	41	41	41
170	gray17	#2B2B2B	43	43	43
171	gray18	#2E2E2E	46	46	46
172	gray19	#303030	48	48	48
173	gray20	#333333	51	51	51
174	gray21	#363636	54	54	54
175	gray22	#383838	56	56	56
176	gray23	#3B3B3B	59	59	59
177	gray24	#3D3D3D	61	61	61
178	gray25	#404040	64	64	64
179	gray26	#424242	66	66	66
180	gray27	#454545	69	69	69
181	gray28	#474747	71	71	71
182	gray29	#4A4A4A	74	74	74
183	gray30	#4D4D4D	77	77	77
184	gray31	#4F4F4F	79	79	79
185	gray32	#525252	82	82	82
186	gray33	#545454	84	84	84
187	gray34	#575757	87	87	87
188	gray35	#595959	89	89	89
189	gray36	#5C5C5C	92	92	92
190	gray37	#5E5E5E	94	94	94
191	gray38	#616161	97	97	97
192	gray39	#636363	99	99	99
193	gray40	#666666	102	102	102
194	gray41	#696969	105	105	105
195	gray42	#6B6B6B	107	107	107
196	gray43	#6E6E6E	110	110	110
197	gray44	#707070	112	112	112
198	gray45	#737373	115	115	115
199	gray46	#757575	117	117	117
200	gray47	#787878	120	120	120

R colors

201	gray48	#7A7A7A	122	122	122
202	gray49	#7D7D7D	125	125	125
203	gray50	#7F7F7F	127	127	127
204	gray51	#828282	130	130	130
205	gray52	#858585	133	133	133
206	gray53	#878787	135	135	135
207	gray54	#8A8A8A	138	138	138
208	gray55	#8C8C8C	140	140	140
209	gray56	#8F8F8F	143	143	143
210	gray57	#919191	145	145	145
211	gray58	#949494	148	148	148
212	gray59	#969696	150	150	150
213	gray60	#999999	153	153	153
214	gray61	#9C9C9C	156	156	156
215	gray62	#9E9E9E	158	158	158
216	gray63	#A1A1A1	161	161	161
217	gray64	#A3A3A3	163	163	163
218	gray65	#A6A6A6	166	166	166
219	gray66	#A8A8A8	168	168	168
220	gray67	#ABABAB	171	171	171
221	gray68	#ADADAD	173	173	173
222	gray69	#B0B0B0	176	176	176
223	gray70	#B3B3B3	179	179	179
224	gray71	#B5B5B5	181	181	181
225	gray72	#B8B8B8	184	184	184
226	gray73	#BABABA	186	186	186
227	gray74	#BDBDBD	189	189	189
228	gray75	#BFBFBF	191	191	191
229	gray76	#C2C2C2	194	194	194
230	gray77	#C4C4C4	196	196	196
231	gray78	#C7C7C7	199	199	199
232	gray79	#C9C9C9	201	201	201
233	gray80	#CCCCCC	204	204	204
234	gray81	#CFCFCF	207	207	207
235	gray82	#D1D1D1	209	209	209
236	gray83	#D4D4D4	212	212	212
237	gray84	#D6D6D6	214	214	214
238	gray85	#D9D9D9	217	217	217
239	gray86	#DBDBDB	219	219	219
240	gray87	#DEDEDE	222	222	222
241	gray88	#E0E0E0	224	224	224
242	gray89	#E3E3E3	227	227	227
243	gray90	#E5E5E5	229	229	229
244	gray91	#E8E8E8	232	232	232
245	gray92	#EBEBEB	235	235	235
246	gray93	#EDED	237	237	237
247	gray94	#F0F0F0	240	240	240
248	gray95	#F2F2F2	242	242	242
249	gray96	#F5F5F5	245	245	245
250	gray97	#F7F7F7	247	247	247
251	gray98	#FAFAFA	250	250	250
252	gray99	#FCFCFC	252	252	252
253	gray100	#FFFFFF	255	255	255
254	green	#00FF00	0	255	0
255	green1	#00FF00	0	255	0
256	green2	#00EE00	0	238	0
257	green3	#00CD00	0	205	0
258	green4	#008B00	0	139	0
259	greenyellow	#ADFF2F	173	255	47
260	grey	#BEBEBE	190	190	190
261	grey0	#000000	0	0	0
262	grey1	#030303	3	3	3
263	grey2	#050505	5	5	5
264	grey3	#080808	8	8	8
265	grey4	#0A0A0A	10	10	10
266	grey5	#0D0D0D	13	13	13
267	grey6	#0F0F0F	15	15	15
268	grey7	#121212	18	18	18
269	grey8	#141414	20	20	20
270	grey9	#171717	23	23	23
271	grey10	#1A1A1A	26	26	26
272	grey11	#1C1C1C	28	28	28
273	grey12	#1F1F1F	31	31	31
274	grey13	#212121	33	33	33
275	grey14	#242424	36	36	36
276	grey15	#262626	38	38	38
277	grey16	#292929	41	41	41
278	grey17	#2B2B2B	43	43	43
279	grey18	#2E2E2E	46	46	46
280	grey19	#303030	48	48	48
281	grey20	#333333	51	51	51
282	grey21	#363636	54	54	54
283	grey22	#383838	56	56	56
284	grey23	#3B3B3B	59	59	59
285	grey24	#3D3D3D	61	61	61
286	grey25	#404040	64	64	64
287	grey26	#424242	66	66	66
288	grey27	#454545	69	69	69
289	grey28	#474747	71	71	71
290	grey29	#4A4A4A	74	74	74
291	grey30	#4D4D4D	77	77	77
292	grey31	#4F4F4F	79	79	79
293	grey32	#525252	82	82	82
294	grey33	#545454	84	84	84
295	grey34	#575757	87	87	87
296	grey35	#595959	89	89	89
297	grey36	#5C5C5C	92	92	92
298	grey37	#5E5E5E	94	94	94
299	grey38	#616161	97	97	97
300	grey39	#636363	99	99	99

R colors

301	grey40	#666666	102	102	102
302	grey41	#696969	105	105	105
303	grey42	#6B6B6B	107	107	107
304	grey43	#6E6E6E	110	110	110
305	grey44	#707070	112	112	112
306	grey45	#737373	115	115	115
307	grey46	#757575	117	117	117
308	grey47	#787878	120	120	120
309	grey48	#7A7A7A	122	122	122
310	grey49	#7D7D7D	125	125	125
311	grey50	#7F7F7F	127	127	127
312	grey51	#828282	130	130	130
313	grey52	#858585	133	133	133
314	grey53	#878787	135	135	135
315	grey54	#8A8A8A	138	138	138
316	grey55	#8C8C8C	140	140	140
317	grey56	#8F8F8F	143	143	143
318	grey57	#919191	145	145	145
319	grey58	#949494	148	148	148
320	grey59	#969696	150	150	150
321	grey60	#999999	153	153	153
322	grey61	#9C9C9C	156	156	156
323	grey62	#9E9E9E	158	158	158
324	grey63	#A1A1A1	161	161	161
325	grey64	#A3A3A3	163	163	163
326	grey65	#A6A6A6	166	166	166
327	grey66	#A8A8A8	168	168	168
328	grey67	#ABABAB	171	171	171
329	grey68	#ADADAD	173	173	173
330	grey69	#B0B0B0	176	176	176
331	grey70	#B3B3B3	179	179	179
332	grey71	#B5B5B5	181	181	181
333	grey72	#B8B8B8	184	184	184
334	grey73	#BABABA	186	186	186
335	grey74	#BDBDBD	189	189	189
336	grey75	#BFBFBF	191	191	191
337	grey76	#C2C2C2	194	194	194
338	grey77	#C4C4C4	196	196	196
339	grey78	#C7C7C7	199	199	199
340	grey79	#C9C9C9	201	201	201
341	grey80	#CCCCCC	204	204	204
342	grey81	#CFCFCF	207	207	207
343	grey82	#D1D1D1	209	209	209
344	grey83	#D4D4D4	212	212	212
345	grey84	#D6D6D6	214	214	214
346	grey85	#D9D9D9	217	217	217
347	grey86	#DBDBDB	219	219	219
348	grey87	#DEDEDE	222	222	222
349	grey88	#E0E0E0	224	224	224
350	grey89	#E3E3E3	227	227	227

351	grey90	#E5E5E5	229	229	229
352	grey91	#E8E8E8	232	232	232
353	grey92	#EBEBEB	235	235	235
354	grey93	#EDEDED	237	237	237
355	grey94	#F0F0F0	240	240	240
356	grey95	#F2F2F2	242	242	242
357	grey96	#F5F5F5	245	245	245
358	grey97	#F7F7F7	247	247	247
359	grey98	#FAFAFA	250	250	250
360	grey99	#FCFCFC	252	252	252
361	grey100	#FFFFFF	255	255	255
362	honeydew	#F0FFF0	240	255	240
363	honeydew1	#F0FFF0	240	255	240
364	honeydew2	#E0EEE0	224	238	224
365	honeydew3	#C1CDC1	193	205	193
366	honeydew4	#838B83	131	139	131
367	hotpink	#FF69B4	255	105	180
368	hotpink1	#FF6EB4	255	110	180
369	hotpink2	#EE6AA7	238	106	167
370	hotpink3	#CD6090	205	96	144
371	hotpink4	#8B3A62	139	58	98
372	indianred	#CD5C5C	205	92	92
373	indianred1	#FF6A6A	255	106	106
374	indianred2	#EE6363	238	99	99
375	indianred3	#CD5555	205	85	85
376	indianred4	#8B3A3A	139	58	58
377	ivory	#FFFFFF0	255	255	240
378	ivory1	#FFFFFF0	255	255	240
379	ivory2	#EEEEE0	238	238	224
380	ivory3	#CDCDC1	205	205	193
381	ivory4	#8B8B83	139	139	131
382	khaki	#F0E68C	240	230	140
383	khaki1	#FFF68F	255	246	143
384	khaki2	#EEE685	238	230	133
385	khaki3	#CDC673	205	198	115
386	khaki4	#8B864E	139	134	78
387	lavender	#E6E6FA	230	230	250
388	lavenderblush	#FFF0F5	255	240	245
389	lavenderblush1	#FFF0F5	255	240	245
390	lavenderblush2	#EEE0E5	238	224	229
391	lavenderblush3	#CDC1C5	205	193	197
392	lavenderblush4	#8B8386	139	131	134
393	lawngreen	#7CFC00	124	252	0
394	lemonchiffon	#FFFACD	255	250	205
395	lemonchiffon1	#FFFACD	255	250	205
396	lemonchiffon2	#EEE9BF	238	233	191
397	lemonchiffon3	#CDC9A5	205	201	165
398	lemonchiffon4	#8B8970	139	137	112
399	lightblue	#ADD8E6	173	216	230
400	lightblue1	#BFEFFF	191	239	255

R colors

401	lightblue2	#B2DFEE	178	223	238
402	lightblue3	#9AC0CD	154	192	205
403	lightblue4	#68838B	104	131	139
404	lightcoral	#F08080	240	128	128
405	lightcyan	#E0FFFF	224	255	255
406	lightcyan1	#E0FFFF	224	255	255
407	lightcyan2	#D1EEEE	209	238	238
408	lightcyan3	#B4CDCD	180	205	205
409	lightcyan4	#7A8B8B	122	139	139
410	lightgoldenrod	#EEDD82	238	221	130
411	lightgoldenrod1	#FFEC8B	255	236	139
412	lightgoldenrod2	#EEDC82	238	220	130
413	lightgoldenrod3	#CDBE70	205	190	112
414	lightgoldenrod4	#8B814C	139	129	76
415	lightgoldenrodyellow	#FAFAD2	250	250	210
416	lightgray	#D3D3D3	211	211	211
417	lightgreen	#90EE90	144	238	144
418	lightgrey	#D3D3D3	211	211	211
419	lightpink	#FFB6C1	255	182	193
420	lightpink1	#FFAEB9	255	174	185
421	lightpink2	#EEA2AD	238	162	173
422	lightpink3	#CD8C95	205	140	149
423	lightpink4	#8B5F65	139	95	101
424	lightsalmon	#FFA07A	255	160	122
425	lightsalmon1	#FFA07A	255	160	122
426	lightsalmon2	#EE9572	238	149	114
427	lightsalmon3	#CD8162	205	129	98
428	lightsalmon4	#8B5742	139	87	66
429	lightseagreen	#20B2AA	32	178	170
430	lightskyblue	#87CEFA	135	206	250
431	lightskyblue1	#B0E2FF	176	226	255
432	lightskyblue2	#A4D3EE	164	211	238
433	lightskyblue3	#8DB6CD	141	182	205
434	lightskyblue4	#607B8B	96	123	139
435	lightslateblue	#8470FF	132	112	255
436	lightslategray	#778899	119	136	153
437	lightslategrey	#778899	119	136	153
438	lightsteelblue	#B0C4DE	176	196	222
439	lightsteelblue1	#CAE1FF	202	225	255
440	lightsteelblue2	#BCD2EE	188	210	238
441	lightsteelblue3	#A2B5CD	162	181	205
442	lightsteelblue4	#6E7B8B	110	123	139
443	lightyellow	#FFFFE0	255	255	224
444	lightyellow1	#FFFFE0	255	255	224
445	lightyellow2	#EEEEED	238	238	209
446	lightyellow3	#CDCDB4	205	205	180
447	lightyellow4	#8B8B7A	139	139	122
448	limegreen	#32CD32	50	205	50
449	linen	#FAF0E6	250	240	230
450	magenta	#FF00FF	255	0	255

451	magenta1	#FF00FF	255	0	255
452	magenta2	#EE00EE	238	0	238
453	magenta3	#CD00CD	205	0	205
454	magenta4	#8B008B	139	0	139
455	maroon	#B03060	176	48	96
456	maroon1	#FF34B3	255	52	179
457	maroon2	#EE30A7	238	48	167
458	maroon3	#CD2990	205	41	144
459	maroon4	#8B1C62	139	28	98
460	mediumaquamarine	#66CDAA	102	205	170
461	mediumblue	#0000CD	0	0	205
462	mediumorchid	#BA55D3	186	85	211
463	mediumorchid1	#E066FF	224	102	255
464	mediumorchid2	#D15FEE	209	95	238
465	mediumorchid3	#B452CD	180	82	205
466	mediumorchid4	#7A378B	122	55	139
467	mediumpurple	#9370DB	147	112	219
468	mediumpurple1	#AB82FF	171	130	255
469	mediumpurple2	#9F79EE	159	121	238
470	mediumpurple3	#8968CD	137	104	205
471	mediumpurple4	#5D478B	93	71	139
472	mediumseagreen	#3CB371	60	179	113
473	mediumslateblue	#7B68EE	123	104	238
474	mediumspringgreen	#00FA9A	0	250	154
475	mediumturquoise	#48D1CC	72	209	204
476	mediumvioletred	#C71585	199	21	133
477	midnightblue	#191970	25	25	112
478	mintcream	#F5FFFA	245	255	250
479	mistyrose	#FFE4E1	255	228	225
480	mistyrose1	#FFE4E1	255	228	225
481	mistyrose2	#EED5D2	238	213	210
482	mistyrose3	#CDB7B5	205	183	181
483	mistyrose4	#8B7D7B	139	125	123
484	moccasin	#FFE4B5	255	228	181
485	navajowhite	#FFDEAD	255	222	173
486	navajowhite1	#FFDEAD	255	222	173
487	navajowhite2	#EECFA1	238	207	161
488	navajowhite3	#CDB38B	205	179	139
489	navajowhite4	#8B795E	139	121	94
490	navy	#000080	0	0	128
491	navyblue	#000080	0	0	128
492	oldlace	#FDF5E6	253	245	230
493	olivedrab	#6B8E23	107	142	35
494	olivedrab1	#C0FF3E	192	255	62
495	olivedrab2	#B3EE3A	179	238	58
496	olivedrab3	#9ACD32	154	205	50
497	olivedrab4	#698B22	105	139	34
498	orange	#FFA500	255	165	0
499	orange1	#FFA500	255	165	0
500	orange2	#EE9A00	238	154	0

R colors

501	orange3	#CD8500	205	133	0
502	orange4	#8B5A00	139	90	0
503	orangered	#FF4500	255	69	0
504	orangered1	#FF4500	255	69	0
505	orangered2	#EE4000	238	64	0
506	orangered3	#CD3700	205	55	0
507	orangered4	#8B2500	139	37	0
508	orchid	#DA70D6	218	112	214
509	orchid1	#FF83FA	255	131	250
510	orchid2	#EE7AE9	238	122	233
511	orchid3	#CD69C9	205	105	201
512	orchid4	#8B4789	139	71	137
513	palegoldenrod	#EEE8AA	238	232	170
514	palegreen	#98FB98	152	251	152
515	palegreen1	#9AFF9A	154	255	154
516	palegreen2	#90EE90	144	238	144
517	palegreen3	#7CCD7C	124	205	124
518	palegreen4	#548B54	84	139	84
519	paleturquoise	#AFEEEE	175	238	238
520	paleturquoise1	#BBFFFF	187	255	255
521	paleturquoise2	#AEeeee	174	238	238
522	paleturquoise3	#96CDCD	150	205	205
523	paleturquoise4	#668B8B	102	139	139
524	palevioletred	#DB7093	219	112	147
525	palevioletred1	#FF82AB	255	130	171
526	palevioletred2	#EE799F	238	121	159
527	palevioletred3	#CD6889	205	104	137
528	palevioletred4	#8B475D	139	71	93
529	papayawhip	#FFEFD5	255	239	213
530	peachpuff	#FFDAB9	255	218	185
531	peachpuff1	#FFDAB9	255	218	185
532	peachpuff2	#EECBAD	238	203	173
533	peachpuff3	#CDAF95	205	175	149
534	peachpuff4	#8B7765	139	119	101
535	peru	#CD853F	205	133	63
536	pink	#FFC0CB	255	192	203
537	pink1	#FFB5C5	255	181	197
538	pink2	#EEA9B8	238	169	184
539	pink3	#CD919E	205	145	158
540	pink4	#8B636C	139	99	108
541	plum	#DDA0DD	221	160	221
542	plum1	#FFBFFF	255	187	255
543	plum2	#EEAEEE	238	174	238
544	plum3	#CD96CD	205	150	205
545	plum4	#8B668B	139	102	139
546	powderblue	#B0E0E6	176	224	230
547	purple	#A020F0	160	32	240
548	purple1	#9B30FF	155	48	255
549	purple2	#912CEE	145	44	238
550	purple3	#7D26CD	125	38	205
551	purple4	#551A8B	85	26	139
552	red	#FF0000	255	0	0
553	red1	#FF0000	255	0	0
554	red2	#EE0000	238	0	0
555	red3	#CD0000	205	0	0
556	red4	#8B0000	139	0	0
557	rosybrown	#BC8F8F	188	143	143
558	rosybrown1	#FFC1C1	255	193	193
559	rosybrown2	#EEB4B4	238	180	180
560	rosybrown3	#CD9B9B	205	155	155
561	rosybrown4	#8B6969	139	105	105
562	royalblue	#4169E1	65	105	225
563	royalblue1	#4876FF	72	118	255
564	royalblue2	#436EEE	67	110	238
565	royalblue3	#3A5FCD	58	95	205
566	royalblue4	#27408B	39	64	139
567	saddlebrown	#8B4513	139	69	19
568	salmon	#FA8072	250	128	114
569	salmon1	#FF8C69	255	140	105
570	salmon2	#EE8262	238	130	98
571	salmon3	#CD7054	205	112	84
572	salmon4	#8B4C39	139	76	57
573	sandybrown	#F4A460	244	164	96
574	seagreen	#2E8B57	46	139	87
575	seagreen1	#54FF9F	84	255	159
576	seagreen2	#4EEE94	78	238	148
577	seagreen3	#43CD80	67	205	128
578	seagreen4	#2E8B57	46	139	87
579	seashell	#FFF5EE	255	245	238
580	seashell1	#FFF5EE	255	245	238
581	seashell2	#EEE5DE	238	229	222
582	seashell3	#CDC5BF	205	197	191
583	seashell4	#8B8682	139	134	130
584	sienna	#A0522D	160	82	45
585	sienna1	#FF8247	255	130	71
586	sienna2	#EE7942	238	121	66
587	sienna3	#CD6839	205	104	57
588	sienna4	#8B4726	139	71	38
589	skyblue	#87CEEB	135	206	235
590	skyblue1	#87CEFF	135	206	255
591	skyblue2	#7EC0EE	126	192	238
592	skyblue3	#6CA6CD	108	166	205
593	skyblue4	#4A708B	74	112	139
594	slateblue	#6A5ACD	106	90	205
595	slateblue1	#836FFF	131	111	255
596	slateblue2	#7A67EE	122	103	238
597	slateblue3	#6959CD	105	89	205
598	slateblue4	#473C8B	71	60	139
599	slategray	#708090	112	128	144
600	slategray1	#6E22FF	198	226	255

R colors

601	slategray2	#B9D3EE	185	211	238
602	slategray3	#9FB6CD	159	182	205
603	slategray4	#6C7B8B	108	123	139
604	slategrey	#708090	112	128	144
605	snow	#FFFAFA	255	250	250
606	snow1	#FFFAFA	255	250	250
607	snow2	#EEE9E9	238	233	233
608	snow3	#CDC9C9	205	201	201
609	snow4	#8B8989	139	137	137
610	springgreen	#00FF7F	0	255	127
611	springgreen1	#00FF7F	0	255	127
612	springgreen2	#00EE76	0	238	118
613	springgreen3	#00CD66	0	205	102
614	springgreen4	#008B45	0	139	69
615	steelblue	#4682B4	70	130	180
616	steelblue1	#63B8FF	99	184	255
617	steelblue2	#5CACEE	92	172	238
618	steelblue3	#4F94CD	79	148	205
619	steelblue4	#36648B	54	100	139
620	tan	#D2B48C	210	180	140
621	tan1	#FFA54F	255	165	79
622	tan2	#EE9A49	238	154	73
623	tan3	#CD853F	205	133	63
624	tan4	#8B5A2B	139	90	43
625	thistle	#D8BFD8	216	191	216
626	thistle1	#FFE1FF	255	225	255
627	thistle2	#EED2EE	238	210	238
628	thistle3	#CDB5CD	205	181	205
629	thistle4	#8B7B8B	139	123	139
630	tomato	#FF6347	255	99	71
631	tomato1	#FF6347	255	99	71
632	tomato2	#EE5C42	238	92	66
633	tomato3	#CD4F39	205	79	57
634	tomato4	#8B3626	139	54	38
635	turquoise	#40E0D0	64	224	208
636	turquoise1	#00F5FF	0	245	255
637	turquoise2	#00E5EE	0	229	238
638	turquoise3	#00C5CD	0	197	205
639	turquoise4	#00868B	0	134	139
640	violet	#EE82EE	238	130	238
641	violetred	#D02090	208	32	144
642	violetred1	#FF3E96	255	62	150
643	violetred2	#EE3A8C	238	58	140
644	violetred3	#CD3278	205	50	120
645	violetred4	#8B2252	139	34	82
646	wheat	#F5DEB3	245	222	179
647	wheat1	#FFE7BA	255	231	186
648	wheat2	#EED8AE	238	216	174
649	wheat3	#CDBA96	205	186	150
650	wheat4	#8B7E66	139	126	102

651	whitesmoke	#F5F5F5	245	245	245
652	yellow	#FFFF00	255	255	0
653	yellow1	#FFFF00	255	255	0
654	yellow2	#EEEE00	238	238	0
655	yellow3	#CDCD00	205	205	0
656	yellow4	#8B8B00	139	139	0
657	yellowgreen	#9ACD32	154	205	50